

Open Energy Knowledge Graph (OEKG)

Interoperable energy scenarios

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Introduction

Energy researchers use a range of assumptions to envision the future of energy systems. Yet, there are significant variations in the methodological approaches, in the data structures, and in the ways results are published. To address these issues, we introduce the **Open Energy Knowledge Graph (OEKG)** to empower users to conveniently describe, upload, explore, and compare different energy scenarios and their projections on multiple factors. To standardize entities and relationships in our knowledge graph, the **Open Energy Ontology (OEO)** is utilized and all associated web-based tools are integrated into the **Open Energy Platform (OEP)**.

Energy scenarios

Energy and climate scenarios are inherently intertwined with complex techno- or socio-economic factors to envision the future of energy systems and discuss the conditions to achieve specific climate or environmental targets.

Energy researchers use various assumptions, parameters, and modelling methodologies to create such scenarios. This leads to the development of multiple studies and scenarios **with different focus and levels of detail**. Often, a lot of effort is needed to pre-process the data from several energy scenarios before an actual comparison can take place.

Ontology

To tackle the challenge of uniformly describing energy scenarios, a harmonized terminology and logical structure is required.

The Open Energy Ontology (OEO) is a domain ontology for energy system analysis, which defines important concepts of the energy domain and their logical relations. It provides a standardized interrelated vocabulary upon which the OEKG is built.

While the OEO functions on a conceptual level, the OEKG operates at an instance level, providing factual information about concrete examples of the concepts defined in the OEO.

Semantic structure

The factual information in the OEKG can be extended and validated based on the conceptualization defined by the OEO.

An example, the OEO contains logical axioms such as: **Solar power technology** \sqsubseteq **Power generation technology** \sqsubseteq **Energy technology**; stating that **Solar power technology** is a kind of **Power generation technology**, which in turn is a kind of **Energy technology**;

The OEKG contains a factual statement for a particular case such as **Covers_technology(Example_study, Solar power technology)**, which states a specific scenario bundle with the name **Example_study** contains the **Solar power technology** as one of its considered technologies.

Applications

Benefits of OEKG:

- It helps to **explore, compare** and **add** information about climate and energy scenarios and their projections.
- Researchers have the opportunity to present their contributions and help build a larger and searchable knowledge-base, open to the public.
- Policy makers will be able to browse available information in an intuitive way that helps them make sense of the wealth of available information.

All of the related open-source tools are available at the following links:

Source code:
<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform>

Website:
<https://openenergy-platform.org/scenario-bundles/main>

Consolidated and Harmonised GHG Emission Projections from European Legislation

Acronym: CHGHG

Contact person(s): Hannah Förster - Christian Winger

Institutions: Öko-Institut e.V.

Funding sources: Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz

Descriptors: Greenhouse gas emissions - CO2 emissions

Abstract: We compiled data and harmonised their notation for GHG emission projection data that European Member States submit under European Legislation mandatorily every two years (and voluntarily in between). The series of tables starts from the GHG emission projections submitted by European Member States in 2014 and is amended as new data becomes available in the reporting platform. (These datasets have the suffix _eio or _exp). The purpose of providing these compilations is to enable straight forward data comparison across the whole series of submissions. We also harmonised data notation across all available submission years for the same datasets but quality checked and approved and compiled by the European Environment Agency (EEA). For these datasets we harmonised data notation across the whole series (These datasets have the suffix _eea).

Scenarios (3)	Publications	Sectors and technology	Models and frameworks
Name: With existing measures scenario			
Acronym: WEM			
Abstract: A with existing measures scenario (WEM) is a policy scenario that includes policy instruments and transformative measures that have been adopted and implemented. The WEM scenario is a mandatory reporting requirement for European Member States, according to European legislation (the latest being the EU Governance Regulation). The datasets provided on the OEP include all European Member States at the submission year. For example, data for the United Kingdom is not available in any datasets submitted after Brexit. For ease, the countries below include all current and former EU Member States. The datasets (suffix _eio) provided includes the WEM scenario data only for those Member States who provided that data.			
Descriptors: with existing measures scenario - emission scenario - greenhouse gas emission scenario - policy scenario - CO2 emission scenario			

Criteria: Scenario abstract Study name Study abstract Descriptors Regions Interacting regions Scenario years Input datasets Output datasets

WEM	WOM	WAM
Descriptors: with existing measures scenario - emission scenario - greenhouse gas emission scenario - policy scenario - CO2 emission scenario	Descriptors: emission scenario - greenhouse gas emission scenario - policy scenario - without measures scenario - CO2 emission scenario	Descriptors: policy scenario - with additional measures scenario
Regions: Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Bulgaria, Germany, France, Finland, Romania, Cyprus, Lithuania, Latvia, Sweden, Ireland, Spain, Luxembourg, Slovenia, Slovakia, Malta, Estonia, Hungary, Greece, Netherlands (the), Portugal, Croatia, Italy, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (the), Ireland, Czechia	Regions: Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Bulgaria, Germany, France, Finland, Romania, Cyprus, Lithuania, Latvia, Sweden, Ireland, Spain, Luxembourg, Slovenia, Slovakia, Malta, Estonia, Hungary, Greece, Netherlands (the), Portugal, Croatia, Italy, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (the), Ireland, Czechia	Regions: Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Bulgaria, Germany, France, Finland, Romania, Cyprus, Lithuania, Latvia, Sweden, Ireland, Spain, Luxembourg, Slovenia, Slovakia, Malta, Estonia, Hungary, Greece, Netherlands (the), Portugal, Croatia, Italy, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (the), Ireland, Czechia
Scenario years: 2020, 2025, 2030, 2035, 2040, 2045, 2050, 2055, 2060, 2065, 2070, 2075, 2080, 2085, 2090, 2095, 2100	Scenario years: 2020, 2025, 2030, 2035, 2040, 2045, 2050, 2055, 2060, 2065, 2070, 2075, 2080, 2085, 2090, 2095, 2100	Scenario years: 2020, 2030, 2040, 2050, 2060, 2070, 2080, 2090, 2100
Output datasets: Rahmendaten für den Projektionsbericht 2023 (Datenblätter) (deutsch)		

Future

Quantitative comparison of scenario projections is not always directly feasible since various datasets have different units, starting points, and trajectories. Also, organizations often focus on specific geographical regions. Therefore, it is essential to consider these **regional** and **temporal differences** when analyzing and comparing energy scenarios. To address these challenges, we plan to develop an **Ontology-Based Data Access (OBDA)** system that enables users to quantitatively compare various energy and climate scenarios.

Perspective: Our primary goal is to promote **transparency** and **interoperability** among energy scenarios. To build a vibrant community around the Open Energy Knowledge Graph, we have a strong emphasis on user participation.

